

TO THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL CULTURE INFLUENCING FACTORS

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Abstract. The article talks about the concept of national culture and factors affecting it. The process of formation and change of national culture is analyzed.

Key words: culture, spirituality, globalization, national culture, resource.

The culture of any nation is not a frozen reality, of course. It is constantly improving under the influence of various conditions and factors. The interpretation of these factors is of particular importance. Because it is possible to understand the laws of its development by identifying and analyzing the factors capable of influencing the national culture. It is true that such factors are characterized by their variety, moreover, their influence on the culture of the nation is also different. However, it is possible to single out the most important ones from the diversity of these factors.

Natural resources are one of the most important factors that shape national culture. The components of the natural environment used in the process of social production to meet the material and spiritual needs of people and society have always been the primary source of material and spiritual blessings. In particular, energetic and non-energetic resources serve as a resource in the implementation of industrial production, and various agro-climatic, land and soil resources, and plant resources in agricultural production. For this reason, natural resources are considered national wealth and are protected by the state. For example, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" states: "... land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national wealth, they must be used wisely and are under state protection." Such a legal position can also be seen in the Constitution.

Our reasoning does not lead to the conclusion that natural resources can be a source for the creation of material goods. True, renewable and renewable natural resources play a decisive role in improving material production. Therefore, their weight in the economy is in constant focus. This is why the head of state sharply criticized the decrease in natural gas production in the country. At the same time, the creation of spiritual blessings also requires material resources. It is difficult to establish the activities of spiritual production facilities without natural resources. Turning the spiritual blessings created by them into

the property of society, preserving, protecting and passing them on to future generations also requires relying on natural resources.

The weight of natural resources determines not only the size of material and spiritual blessings, but also the pace of national cultural development. In other words, if the country's economy is provided with natural resources, the national culture will develop rapidly. This can be seen, for example, in the example of the national cultures of countries such as the USA, Germany, France, China, and Saudi Arabia. The shortage of natural resources, on the contrary, has a negative impact on the development of national culture.

At this point, it is necessary to dwell on two aspects of the issue. First, the presence of natural resources in a country does not automatically lead to the development of national culture. For this, it is necessary to use them wisely. It is known that natural resources are managed differently in different countries. In particular, the mobilization of natural resources for social development in some countries is surprising. In this regard, the People's Republic of China can be cited as an example. A country where half of the population lived in poverty half a century ago, today has the most mature economy in the world. These victories were achieved due to rational use of natural resources. And the economic development created a foundation for the development of national language, traditions, values, literature and art. In other countries of the group, the irrational use of natural resources and the fact that they make a living simply by exporting them also affects the pace of development of national culture.

Secondly, the lack of natural resources in the country does not necessarily mean that the national culture will decline. Today, a number of countries are solving the shortage of natural resources in their own way. For example, Japan has long suffered from a shortage of natural resources. Therefore, special attention is paid to the use of recreational resources in the country (natural complexes, cultural and historical monuments, economic potential of the country, intellectual potential of society, etc.). In this regard, the accumulated income is spent on the purchase of necessary natural resources.

However, regardless of the above-mentioned two cases, the natural resource remains a shaping factor of national culture. First of all, it serves as a locomotive in the economy, and economic development lays the foundation for the development of the structural elements of national culture, national language, national tradition, national ritual, national value, cultural heritage, national literature, national art, and national education.

Natural resources are only objective conditions for the formation of national culture. Moreover, its impact on the national culture is not direct, but indirect. The literal creators of national cultural artifacts, their concentration and transmitters are social institutions. In general, a social institution is understood as an organization created and formed historically in order to organize the joint life activities of people. “Ижтимоий институтларни ташкил этувчи асос вазифасини ижтимоий алоқалар, конкрет индивидлар, ижтимоий гуруҳлар ва жамоаларнинг ўзаро алоқалари ва муносабатлари ўтайди.” The formation of such institutions is not a spontaneous process. It arises in response to the need to satisfy certain social, economic, political or cultural needs. For the formation of this or that social institution, first of all, the need for it should arise, the satisfaction of this need should become the main goal of a certain group of people, the norms of activities leading to the goal should be decided, and the roles performed at the level of the institution should be defined.

Today, the concept of "social institution" is used in different meanings and perspectives. For example, in scientific sources, expressions such as family institution, educational institution, healthcare institution, state power institution, and religious institution can be found. This indicates the rather complex nature of social institutions. It should also be noted that not all social institutions operating in the society have an official character. Functions performed in official social institutions are coordinated with the help of certain norms, methods and tools. For example, the state, court, army, family, school, university, etc. can be included in the group of such institutions. They perform their duties based on specific regulations. However, in contrast to them, at any stage of social development, informal social institutions that have arisen on the basis of common interests of people and are not subject to any norms also operate. Although the scope of activities of these institutions is not coordinated by any official document, they also play an important role in the life of society.

One of the points that unites any formal and informal social institutions is that they all act as a factor in the formation of national culture in society. This can be seen in the following. First, social institutions operating in the society take an active part in the creation of artifacts of national culture. In this regard, the role of associations uniting linguists and writers, poets and writers, painters and photographers, actors and directors, hafiz and composers, craftsmen and artisans should be highlighted.

Secondly, social institutions serve to enrich the national culture with a new element. For example, although national traditions and customs in the society have a stable character, they are not completely unchanging phenomena. Over time, they are filled with new and new aspects, features, nuances as a result of the activity of institutions such as family, neighborhood, educational institution.

Thirdly, as a result of the activity of social institutions, various values, traditions and norms take place in social life. In short, social institutions are the power that gives a special spirit to all the elements of national culture and makes them move.

Fourthly, social institutes, while performing their socio-cultural function, ensure adherence to the elements of national culture through various cultural activities, which they promote and promote. They are also the main subject that implements national traditions and customs and conducts cultural events.

Fifth, social institutions make it possible to transmit national cultural artifacts to future generations. In other words, succession in national culture is ensured by the efforts of social institutions

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